

Gravity and the Motion of Light

Revealing why General and Special Relativity are Wrong

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Abstract.

On this paper, I present realisations and assessments proposing a reality different from what the scientific community believes that exist regarding the motion of light, and different from what general and special relativity propose!

People think that a source of light that is stationary relative to them is located at the hypothetical centre of the spherical waves of light that it emits towards all directions.

This is wrong!

A source of light that is stationary relative to us, it is not located at the hypothetical centre of the spherical light waves that it emits towards all directions!

For example, a light bulb in your room or on the street, is not at the hypothetical centre of the spherical waves of light that it emits, even though it is stationary relative to you!!!

In fact, the reality is that most of the light sources on the Universe are not located at the hypothetical centre of the waves of light that they emit towards all directions!

The fact that light sources are not at the hypothetical centre of the spherical waves of light that they emit towards all directions, means that **there is anisotropy of the motion of light relative to its source**, and leads to the **detection of changes in the energy of the photons** that the source has emit, even though the source has emitted identical photons towards all directions!

My ideas correlate to Quantum Physics, the Sagnac effect on the GPS systems, and the Michelson-Gale-Pearson experiment.

Introduction.

Special and general relativity play a fundamental role in physics for many years, and the majority of scientists believe that special and general relativity are correct.

On this paper, I will present realisations and assessments presenting a reality different from what the scientific community believes that exist regarding the motion of light, and different than what relativity proposes!!!

My opinion is that special and general relativity are wrong, and on this paper I will explain why!!!

People think that a source of light that is stationary relative to them it is located at the hypothetical centre of the spherical waves of light that it emits towards all directions.

This is wrong!!!

A source of light that is stationary relative to us, it is not located at the hypothetical centre of the spherical light waves that it emits towards all directions, even if it is at an inertial reference frame!!!

For example: A light bulb in your room or on the street, is not at the hypothetical centre of the spherical waves of light that it emits, even though it is stationary relative to you!

Another example: A light source somewhere in our solar system and away from a planet is not located at the hypothetical centre of the spherical waves of light that it emits towards all directions, regardless of whether it is stationary relative to you as an observer, and regardless of whether or not it is at an inertial reference frame!

The reality on the Universe is that most of the light sources are not located at the hypothetical centre of the waves of light that they are emitting towards all directions!!!

The energy on the photons changes for the same reason that the energy on other particles changes, and that reason is different relative speed because **there is anisotropy of the speed of light relative to its source**, which is connected to the fact that a source of light is not located at the hypothetical centre of the spherical light waves that it emits!!!

First, let's see what we will call **isotropy & anisotropy** of the motion of light relative to its source.

When we use the terms **isotropy & anisotropy** we refer to differences dependent on direction! This means that if we talk about the motion of light relative to its source, we focus on the motion of light relative to its source towards different directions!

So, in order to say that the motion of the light that a source has emit is **isotropic** relative to the source, the light that the source has emit must move in the same way towards all directions relative to the source!

If the light is not moving in the same way towards all directions relative to the source, then we will say that the motion of light relative to its source is **anisotropic!**

What does this mean?

Suppose that we have a light source that for a period of time does not emit light, for example a light bulb that is switched off, and at some point the source is switched on and emits a light wave towards all directions, meaning that it emits a spherical light wave!

In order to say that the motion of the light wave is **isotropic** relative to its source, meaning to say that the relative speed between the source and the light wave is the same towards all directions, as the light wave is moving away from the source the distance between the source and the wavefront must be the same towards all directions, and this means that the source must be at the hypothetical centre of the wave of light that it has emit/produce(**light source A** on the **figure 1**)!!!

If as the light wave is moving away from the source, the distance between the light source and the wavefront is not the same towards all directions, this means that we must say that the relative speed between the source and the light wave is not the same towards all directions, and this is **anisotropy** of the motion of the light wave relative to its source, and in this case the source is **not** at the hypothetical centre of the light wave that it has emit(**light source B** on the **figure 1**)!!!

If as the light wave is moving away from its source we don't have the same distance between the source and the wavefront towards all directions(like the **light source B** in the **figure 1**), this means that we must say that the relative speed between the light source and some parts of the light wave is slower when these parts of the wave are closer to the source, and the relative speed between the light source and some other parts of the light wave is higher when these parts of the wave are farther away from the source!!!

If the distance between the source and the wavefront is the same towards all directions(like the **light source A** on the **figure 1**), this means that we must say that all the parts of the wavefront towards all directions have the same speed relative to the source!

Figure 1

Figure 1. If the source of the light wave is at the hypothetical centre of the wave, as the **light source A** does, in this case we have isotropy of the speed of light relative to this specific source. If the source of the light wave is not at the hypothetical centre of the wave, as the **light source B** does, in this case we have anisotropy of the speed of light relative to this specific source.

- If we say that there is anisotropy of the motion of light relative to its source, that statement does not contradict to the fact that the motion of light does not depend on the motion of the source!

The fact that the motion of light does not depend on the motion of the source, it's actually the reason why there is anisotropy of the motion of light relative to its source! -

An important note regarding the Michelson-Morley experiment that will help us understand the relation between the light source and the expanding light wave.

The Michelson-Morley experiment was conducted in an attempt to detect the anisotropy of the speed of light.

The light source that was used in the experiment was stationary on the surface of the Earth. According to the findings of the experiment, there was no anisotropy of the speed of light!!! But, what it means if we accept as reality the findings of the experiment?

The light source on the experiment did not emit circular or spherical light waves, but let's imagine that it did emit circular or spherical light waves!

What it means about the relation between the source and the light waves that the source has emit, if we accept that there is isotropy of the speed of light relative to the source?

It means that the light source that was used on the experiment, and was stationary on the surface of the Earth, was at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that it has emitted, meaning that, according to the result of the experiment, we were having the situation that we see for the **light source A** on the **figure 1!!!**

But, what if the findings of the experiment were showing that there was anisotropy of the speed of light relative to the source???

If the results of the experiment were showing that there was anisotropy of the speed of light relative to the source, in this case we would have to say that the light source was not at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that it has emitted, meaning that we would be having the situation that we see for the **light source B** on the **figure 1!!!**

It is that simple!

If we say that there is isotropy of the speed of light relative to a source, this means that the light source is at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that it will emit!!!

If the light source is not at the hypothetical centre of the light waves, in this case we have anisotropy of the speed of light relative to the source!!!

A very significant realisation.

Suppose that somewhere(anywhere, it doesn't matter where) there are two sources of light (point sources) that are moving towards each other{**figure 2,(a)**}.

We call them **light sources A & B**.

The light sources are in relative motion with each other at constant relative speed and **both light sources are in an inertial reference frame.**

The sources currently do not emit light.

At some point the **light source A** and the **light source B** are next to each other{**figure 2,(b)**}.

When the two sources of light are next to each other{**figure 2,(b)**}, each source will emit light towards all directions.

Figure 2. When the two light sources are next to each other{figure 2,(b)}, both they will emit light towards all directions.

After the emission of the light, the sources are moving away from each other because their relative motion continues.

Two waves of light will be created, one from the light emitted by the **light source A** and the other from the light emitted by the **light source B**(**figures 3 & 4**).

(The waves will be "three-dimensional waves" or in other words "spherical waves" because they will form an expanding sphere since the sources emit light towards all directions, but of course in the figures 3 & 4 we see "two-dimensional waves" or in other words "circular waves".)

As we know from many experiments, the motion of all photons in an area is the same regardless of the motion of their source!!!

So, the two light waves will expand with exactly the same way(**figures 3 & 4**)!!!

Not only the motion of the photons emitted by the two sources will not depend on the motion of the light sources, but moreover, the photons which are emitted by the two light sources will make identical motion, and that's why the two light waves will expand in exactly the same way(**figures 3 & 4**)!!!

Figure 3

Figure 3. Presents the case where the one source is not at the centre of the light wave, meaning that there is **anisotropy of the motion of light for the one source**. The light source B is not at the hypothetical centre of its own light wave. There cannot be both sources at the centre of their own light wave, which means that at least for the one source there is anisotropy of the speed of light.

So, there are two light waves which expand in exactly the same way, and also there are two light sources which are in relative motion with each other, and here is the important realisation: There are two possibilities:

- First possibility(**figure 3**): Only the one of the two sources will be at the hypothetical centre of its own light wave.
- Second possibility(**figure 4**): Both light sources will not be at the hypothetical centre of their own light wave.

The possibility of having both light sources to be located at the centre of their own light wave does not exist!!!

We cannot have both the **light source A** and the **light source B** at the hypothetical centre of their light wave!!!

Figure 4

Figure 4. Presents the case where both light sources are not at the centre of their own light wave, meaning that there is anisotropy of the motion of light for both sources. Two waves of light will be created, and those two light waves will expand exactly in the same way, regardless of the fact that their sources are in relative motion with each other.

It doesn't matter where this example/experiment is taken place in the Universe, and it doesn't matter if one or both sources are making linear motion or if they revolve around something!!! Only the one of the two light sources can be at the hypothetical centre of its own light wave!!! The other possible reality is that both light sources will not be at the centre of their own light wave, but there cannot be both light sources at the centre of their own light wave!!!

Why?

Because the photons that the two sources have emit will move exactly the same and the two light waves will expand with exactly the same way(figure 3 & 4), but the two light sources will move away from each other because they are in relative motion with each other!!!

Let's focus on the case which is depicted in the **figure 3**, meaning in the case where the one of the two light sources is at the centre of its own light wave.

The two light sources are in relative motion with each other at constant relative speed and both sources are in an inertial reference frame, meaning that each source considers itself as being at rest, as stationary!!!

But even though this happens, even though both light sources are in an inertial reference frame, the motion of the light waves relative to the sources is not the same for the two sources (**figure 3**), because the **light source A** is at the centre of its own light wave but the **light source B** is not at the centre of its own light wave!!!

The two sources have emit light towards all directions, but as the light is moving away from the sources, the distance between the **light source B** and the light wave is not the same towards all directions(**figure 3**)!!!

As the photons that the **light source B** has emit are moving away from the source, some photons are closer to the source and some photons are farther away from the source(**figure 3**)!

This means that there is anisotropy of the speed of light for the light source B(figure 3)!

On the **figure 3**, isotropy of the speed of light occurs only for the **light source A**!

Let's focus on the case which is depicted in the **figure 4**, meaning in the case where both sources are not at the hypothetical centre of its own light wave.

The two sources have emit light towards all directions, but as the light is moving away from the sources, the distance between the sources and the light wave is not the same towards all directions, and this applies to both sources(figure 4)!!!

As the photons that each source has emit are moving away from the source, some photons are closer to the source and some photons are farther away from the source, and this applies for both sources(figure 4)!!!

So, we have a case where both sources consider themselves as stationary because both are in an inertial reference frame, but as we see in the **figure 4**, for both sources the distance between the source and the wave is not the same towards all directions, meaning that for both sources there is anisotropy of the speed of light!!!

The other possibility is that there will be anisotropy of the speed of light for only the one source, in the case where the other source is at the centre of its own wave(**figure 3**)!!!

But, the possibility to have isotropy of the speed of light for both sources does not exist because the possibility to have both sources at the hypothetical centre of their own light wave does not exist!!!

An extremely important realisation:

If we are having more light sources at the same location in relative motion with each other instead of two that we see on the previous example, for example a million light sources, either all of them would not be at the hypothetical centre of their own light waves, or only one of the million sources may be at the hypothetical centre of the light wave that it has emit!!!

So, the normality in the Universe is that light sources are not at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that they emit, meaning that the anisotropy of the speed of light relative to its source is the normality!!!

On the **figure 3** example, any light source that is on the move relative to the **light source A** will not be at the hypothetical centre of its own light wave!

A significant error of the scientific community.

There is a big error of the scientific community when they try to explain the "doppler effect" in light, which is an error in the way that we think that the light is moving away from the source!!!

It is an error which has to do with the position of the light source in relation to the expanding light waves!!!

When people want to depict a case where a light source and an observer (human, car, spaceship, etc.) are stationary relative to each other, they always place the light source at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that it has emit!!!

But this is totally wrong because, whether or not an observer is stationary relative to a source is unrelated to whether or not the source is at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that it has emit!!!

We can have a case where a light source and an observer are stationary relative to each other and the light source will not be at the hypothetical centre of the light waves!!!

It is wrong to think that the source is always at the hypothetical centre of the light waves when there is no relative motion between us and the source!!!

It is totally wrong to correlate the fact that there is no relative motion between the source and the observer with the probability of the source being at the centre of its own light waves!!!

Also, when people want to depict a case where the observer is on the move but the source is not, again they always place the light source at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that it has emit!!!

They are depicting the light source not at the hypothetical centre of the waves only when they are depicting the source to be on the move and the observer is not!!!

If for example we have a light source and a human in relative motion with each other, when they depict the human on the move they have the source at the hypothetical centre of the light waves, but when they depict the source on the move they have the source not at the centre of the light waves!!!

But this is totally wrong!!!

Whether or not the light source is at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that it has emit, is unrelated to whether or not there is relative motion between an observer and the source!!!

Whether or not the light source is at the hypothetical centre of its own light waves, is something that must be evaluated independently from anything else!!!

Now, after we clarified some things, let's see what is happening.

With the help of the Michelson-Gale-Pearson experiment, the "Sagnac effect" and the "Sagnac effect" on the GPS systems, we can understand that **the speed of light is not isotropic** relative to a source which is stationary on the surface of the Earth!!!

When Albert A. Michelson saw that he could not detect anisotropy of the speed of light with the Michelson-Morley experiment, he came up with an idea for another experiment that could detect the **anisotropy of the speed of light due to the Earth's rotation!!!**

That experiment was the Michelson-Gale-Pearson experiment!!!

Michelson came up with this idea about that new experiment because the tangential speed of the Earth's surface is too small, and the Michelson-Morley experiment was not accurate enough in such small speeds!!!

But, what the Michelson-Gale-Pearson experiment and the "Sagnac effect" are showing?

The Michelson-Gale-Pearson experiment and the "Sagnac effect" are showing that **a light source which is stationary in the surface of the Earth, will not be located at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that it will emit towards all directions(light bulb A on the figures 5, 6, 7)!!!**

A light source that is stationary on the surface of the Earth, is a light source that revolves around the Earth's axis due to the Earth's rotation!!!

A light source that is stationary on the surface of the Earth (**light bulb A** on the **figures 5,6,7**), is a light source at rest in the "Earth-centered, Earth-fixed"(ECEF) frame.

A light source that is stationary on the surface of the Earth, is on the move relative to the "Earth-centered inertial"(ECI) frame, and it will not be at the hypothetical centre of the waves of light that it will emit(see **light bulb A** on the **figures 5, 6, 7**)!!!

The fact that the light source(see **light bulb A** on the **figures 5, 6, 7**) is not at the centre of the light wave that it has emit, means that we must say that there is anisotropy of the speed of light relative to this source!!!

If we accept the result of the Michelson-Morley experiment as true, we must say that a light source which is stationary on the surface of the Earth is at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that it will emit towards all directions!!!

In that case, in the example that I present in the **figures 5-6-7**, the **light bulb A** must be at the hypothetical centre of its own light waves, but the **light bulb B** will not be at the hypothetical centre of its own light waves, because there cannot be both light bulbs at the hypothetical centre of their own light waves, because they are in relative motion with each other!!!

But the **light bulb B** is stationary on the ECI frame, so, can it not be at the hypothetical centre of its own light waves?

Important note.

A light source that is stationary on the surface of the Earth, is at the centre of the light wave that it will emit, only if it is located at the point where the Earth's axis of rotation meet the surface!!!

A light source located at the point where the Earth's axis of rotation meet the surface, is stationary in the "Earth-centered inertial"(ECI) frame.

Any source of light which is stationary on the surface of the Earth but it is away from the point where the axis of the rotation meet the surface, it will not be at the centre of the light wave that it will emit, because it is on the move inside the gravitational field of the Earth and it is on the move in the "Earth-centered inertial"(ECI) frame, and that happens due to the Earth's rotation.

If a light source is not revolving/rotating at all around the Earth's axis, meaning a light source stationary on the "Earth-centered inertial"(ECI) frame, that light source will be at the centre of the light wave that it will emit(see **light bulb B** on the **figures 5, 6, 7**) because it is stationary inside the gravitational field of the Earth!!!

But, I'm talking about a source which is very close to the surface of the Earth!!!

If the source is far away from the planet, it will not be at the centre of its own light wave if it is stationary on the "Earth-centered inertial"(ECI) frame because it is far away from the influence of the Earth's gravity!!!

Figure 5. In this image I have put an arrow on the light bulb A, the human and the trees, indicating that they are moving towards the East as the Earth rotates. The light bulb A is stationary on the surface of the Earth, which means that the light bulb A revolves with the Earth around the Earth's axis, meaning that the light bulb A is stationary on the "Earth-centered, Earth-fixed"(ECEF) frame. The light bulb B is stationary on the "Earth-centered inertial"(ECI) frame, which means that the light bulb B does not revolve around the axis of the Earth. The light bulb B is standing a few metres above the surface of the Earth.

On the **figure 5**, the **human** the **trees** and the **light bulb A** are stationary on the surface of the Earth meaning that they are actually revolving with the Earth around its axis, meaning that they are moving towards the East as the Earth rotates!!!

The **light bulb B**(**figure 5**) is stationary on the "Earth-centered inertial"(ECI) frame, meaning that the **light bulb B** is not revolving at all around the axis of the Earth!!!

The **light bulb B** stands a few metres above the surface of the Earth.

To a human stationary on the ground, the **light bulb B**(**figure 5**) will appear moving towards the West, like also the Sun and the Stars appear moving towards the West, because the human is moving towards the East due to the rotation of the Earth!!!

The **light bulb B**(**figure 5**) represents a light bulb that is stationary on the "Earth-centered inertial"(ECI) frame, meaning that it does not revolve in any way around the Earth, but it is on the move relative to the surface of the Earth due to the Earth's rotation.

The **human** and the **light bulb A** are on the move relative to the **light bulb B** because they revolve/rotate with the Earth, or we can say that the **light bulb B** is on the move relative to the **human** and the **light bulb A**!!!

The **light bulb A** and the **light bulb B** are in relative motion with each other(**figure 5**).

As we have seen on the previous example in the **figures 3 & 4**, if two sources of light are in relative motion with each other, only the one source may be at the centre of its own wave of light, meaning that, on the **figure 5** example, we cannot have both the **light bulb A** and the **light bulb B** at the centre of their own wave of light!!!

The **light bulb A**(**figure 5**) is not at the hypothetical centre of its own light wave because it is moving towards the East due to the rotation of the Earth!!!

As we see on the **figure 5 example**, the distance B is smaller than the distance A, meaning that as the photons are moving away from the source, some photons that the source has emit are closer to the source and some are farther away from the source, which means that in this case we must say that there is **anisotropy of the speed of light relative to the source**, which is the **light bulb A**!!!

The distance A(**figure 5**) is the distance between the **light bulb A** and the photons that are emitted towards the West, and the distance B(**figure 5**) is the distance between the **light bulb A** and the photons emitted towards the East!!!

As we see on the **figure 5**, we must say that the relative speed between the **light bulb A** and the photons that are emitted towards the East is smaller than the relative speed between the **light bulb A** and the photons emitted towards the West!!!

All the photons that the **light bulb A** emits are making the same motion not relative to the light bulb A, but relative to something else!!!

The **human** on the **figure 5** represents a human who is stationary on the surface of the Earth. The **light bulb A**(**figure 5**) is also stationary on the surface of the Earth.

So, the **light bulb A** is stationary relative to the **human**, but the **light bulb A** is not located at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that it emits, which is contrary to the belief of the scientific community, because if the **human** on the **figure 5** is a scientist, he will believe that the **light bulb A** must be at the centre of the light waves!!!

The scientific community believes two things:

1. A light source stationary relative to an observer is at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that it has emit towards all directions.
2. A light source that is stationary at the surface of the Earth is at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that it has emit(Michelson-Morley experiment).

So, if the human on the **figure 5** is a scientist, he will believe that the **light bulb A** is at the centre of the light waves!!!

But this belief is wrong!

Both beliefs(1 & 2) that we see above are wrong!

All the findings are showing that a source of light that is stationary in the surface of the Earth (meaning that it revolves around the axis of the Earth because it rotates with the Earth) is not at the centre of the light wave that it will emit!!!

Also, all the findings are showing that a source of light that is very close to the surface of the Earth and it is stationary on the ECI frame, meaning that is not revolving around the Earth, will be at the centre of the light wave that it will emit, or maybe it is approximately at the centre of the light wave(it depends on how strong is the Earth's gravity)!!!

But, this is what is happening to sources very close to the surface of the Earth!!!

If a source of light is far away from the Earth, it will not be at the centre of its own light wave even if it is stationary on the ECI frame!!!

The possibility for a source of light away from a planet to be at the centre of its own light wave is extremely small!!!

But not only away from a planet, in general the possibility for a source of light to be at the centre of its own light wave is extremely small!!!

What if someone disagrees with what I say?

What if someone, due to the fact he accepts as true the result of the Michelson-Morley experiment, believes that the **light bulb A** is actually at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that it has emit, because it is stationary on the surface of the Earth?

If we say that the **light bulb A** is at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that it has emit, then we must say that the **light bulb B** is not at the hypothetical centre of its own light waves, because the two light bulbs are in relative motion with each other!!!

And not only the **light bulb B**, but every light source on the planet that is not stationary on the surface of the Earth will not be at the hypothetical centre of its own light waves!!

In this case, the **light bulb B** can be stationary relative to a human, but it will not be at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that it emits towards all directions!!!

Therefore, regardless of which of the two light bulbs we think that is at the hypothetical centre of the light waves, we will have a case where a light source(light bulb A or B) is stationary relative to a human but it will not be at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that it emits towards all directions!!!

And there is the case where both light bulbs will not be at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that they will emit, while both light bulbs being stationary relative to a human!!!

Why?

Because either one of the two light bulbs in the **figure 5** is at the hypothetical centre of its own light waves, or both are not at the hypothetical centre of their own light waves!!!

Important note.

In recent years have been conducted a few Michelson-Morley type experiments using lasers, optical resonators, cryogenic oscillators, etc.

According to these new experiments there is no anisotropy to a level of 10^{-15} , 10^{-16} or even 10^{-17} when comparing the speed of light on the two perpendicular paths where it moves.

The problem with the Michelson-Morley type experiments is that the tangential speed of the surface of the Earth is extremely small compared to the speed of light!!!

The tangential speed of the surface on the equator is 465 metres/second!!!

According to my calculations, in a latitude where the tangential speed of the surface of the Earth is 340 metres/second we will not find anisotropy on the scale of 10^{-13} while using interferometer experiments.

According to my calculations we must go to a level of 10^{-14} and lower to find anisotropy while using interferometer experiments, but down to that extremely low scales the probability of an error is extremely high.

Down to that extremely low scales, the smallest error on the high number of variables that we must take into account and the smallest error on the way that we conduct the experiment, leads to results in calculations that do not respond to reality!!!

This means that we cannot rely on the results of these experiments!!!

These experiments involve sources of light that are stationary on the surface of the Earth, meaning that they are stationary on the ECEF frame!!!

If we accept that the findings of these experiments are correct and there is no anisotropy, this means that we must accept that a light source which is stationary on the surface of the Earth, meaning stationary on the ECEF frame, is at the hypothetical centre of the wave of light that it will emit!!!

But if we accept that, then we must accept that a source of light which is stationary on the ECI frame, and it is on the move on the ECEF frame, will not be at the hypothetical centre of the wave of light that it will emit, meaning that if we say that the **light bulb A** on the examples in the **figures 5-6-7** is at the hypothetical centre of the light waves, then we must say that that **light bulb B** on these figures will not be at the hypothetical centre of the light waves!!!

Explanation and analysis.

Suppose that the **light bulb A** is stationary at the surface of the Earth on the Equator(**figure 6**), meaning that it is stationary on the "Earth-centered, Earth-fixed"(ECEF) frame.

The **light bulb A** rotates/revolves around the axis of the Earth, because it rotates with the Earth, meaning that it is on the move relative to the "Earth-centered-inertial"(ECI) frame.

We can use the terms "rotate" & "revolve" in order to describe the motion of the **light bulb A** (**figure 6**) around the axis of the Earth, but we can also use the term "orbit"!!!

The **light bulb A** is stationary relative to the surface of the Earth, but it orbits around the axis of the Earth as it rotates with the Earth!!!!

Figure 6

Figure 6. The light bulb A is stationary at the surface of the Earth on the equator, meaning that it revolves/rotates with the Earth. The light bulb A is stationary on the ECEF frame and is moving towards the East as the Earth rotates. The light bulb B is also on the equator but is standing a few centimetres above the ground and it is stationary on the "Earth-centered inertial"(ECI) frame, meaning that it does not revolve around the Earth's axis. While the Earth rotates, the light bulb A passes next to the light bulb B, like we see on the figure 7.

Suppose there is another light bulb on the Equator, the **light bulb B**(figure 6), but that light bulb stands a few centimetres above the ground and is not revolving around the axis of the Earth, meaning that it is stationary on the "Earth-centered-inertial"(ECI) frame.

The **light bulb B** is a few centimetres above the ground in order to be close to the **light bulb A** (A light bulb that is a few centimetres above the ground and it is stationary on the ECI frame will collide with the ground as the Earth rotates because the Earth is not a perfect sphere and has mountains, so, to help you visualise the whole situation is better to consider the Earth as a perfect and smooth sphere with no mountains.

The purpose of this example is to make a point and to help you understand, so, just imagine that the Earth is a perfect sphere.)

Figure 7. The figures 7,(a) & 7,(b) depict how the situation will look like if we are above the light bulbs and we are looking down towards the surface of the Earth. The light bulb A is stationary on the surface of the Earth on the equator, which means that it revolves/rotates around the axis of the Earth due to the rotation of the Earth and is moving towards the East. The light bulb B is also at the equator but it is standing a few centimetres above the ground and does not revolve/rotate around the axis of the Earth, meaning that it is stationary on the ECI reference frame. When the light bulb A passes next to the light bulb B {figure 7,(a)} both light bulbs will emit light towards all directions. Two waves of light will be created {figure 7,(b)}, and the light bulb A will not be at the hypothetical centre of its own light wave.

So, the **light bulb A** rotates/revolves with the Earth around the axis of rotation, but the **light bulb B** does not rotate/revolve around the axis of the Earth (figure 6).

While the Earth rotates, the **light bulb A** passes next to the **light bulb B** {figure 7,(a)}.

(The **figure 7** depict how the situation will look like if we are above the light bulbs and we are looking down towards the surface of the Earth.)

When the **light bulb A** passes next to the **light bulb B** {figure 7,(a)} the two light bulbs will emit light towards all directions.

Two waves of light will be created, one from the light emitted by the light bulb A and the other from the light emitted by the light bulb B {figure 7,(b)}.

The two light waves will expand with exactly the same way because the motion of the light is unrelated to the motion of the source {figure 7, (b)}.

Not only the motion of the light will not depend on the motion of the light bulbs/sources, but moreover, the photons which are emitted by the two light bulbs/sources will make identical motion!!!

So, we can say that there will be created two light waves which will be stationary relative to each other!!!

And here is the important part:

We cannot have both the **light bulb A** and the **light bulb B** at the hypothetical centre of their own light wave{**figure 7,(b)**}!!!

Only the one of the two light bulbs/sources can be at the centre of its own light wave, and the other possible reality is that both light bulbs/sources will not be at the centre of their light wave, but we cannot have both light bulbs/sources at the centre of their light wave!!!

Why?

Because the two light waves will expand with exactly the same way{**figure 7,(b)**}, but the two light bulbs/sources are on the move relative to each other!!!

And as we can understand from the "Sagnac effect" and the Michelson-Gale-Pearson experiment, a light source which is stationary in the surface of the Earth on the Equator and is revolving around the axis of the Earth is not at the hypothetical centre of its own light wave, and a light source which is not revolving around the Earth's axis is at the hypothetical centre of its own light wave, meaning that the **light bulb B** will be at the centre of the light wave, and the light bulb A will not be at the centre of the light wave {figure 7,(b)}.

Due to the rotation of the Earth the **light bulb A** is moving towards the East, and the result is that it will not be at the hypothetical centre of its own light wave{**figure 7,(b)**}!!!

(The **figures 7,(a) & 7,(b)** depict how the situation will look like if we are above the two light bulbs and we are looking down towards the surface of the Earth.

The two light bulbs are passing the one next to the other in our line of sight.)

Either the **light bulb A**(stationary on the ECEF frame) is at the centre of the light wave and the **light bulb B** is not, or the **light bulb B**(stationary on the ECI frame) is at the centre of the light wave and the **light bulb A** is not, or both are not at the centre of the light wave(see figures 3 & 4)!

So, either there is anisotropy of the speed of light for the **light bulb A**, or for the **light bulb B**, or for both (figures 5-6-7)!

On the example in the **figures 6 & 7** the light bulb A is making revolutionary motion around the axis of the Earth!!!

If the light bulb A was making linear motion the result would have been the same!!!

Imagine a scenario where the two light bulbs are in relative motion with each other at constant relative speed but the light bulb A is not making revolutionary motion!!!

Imagine that the light bulb A is making linear motion and is coming from far away from the Earth, it will pass next to the light bulb B and will move away from the Earth.

In this scenario we would have again the same result, meaning that the light bulb A will again not be at the centre of its own light wave!

We can say that there is isotropy of the speed of light relative to a source only when the source is at the hypothetical centre of the light wave that it has emit!

The **light bulb B**{figure 7,(b)} is at the hypothetical centre of its own light wave which means that there is isotropy of the speed of light relative to this source!!!

The fact that the **light bulb A**{figure 7,(b)} is not at the hypothetical centre of its own light wave, means that there is anisotropy of the speed of light relative to this specific light source! But, this anisotropy is not the result of a different motion of the light that it is emitted from the **light bulb A!!!**

On the contrary, the light emitted from the **light bulb A** is making the exact same motion with the light emitted from the **light bulb B**, and that's why the two waves of light which are produced by the two light bulbs are expanding with exactly the same way{figure 7,(b)}!!!

But, in order to say which is the relative speed between the photons and the light bulbs, we must focus on what the photons are doing in relation to the light bulbs, and not on what the photons are doing relative to each other!!!

All the photons that the **light bulb A** emits are making the same motion but not relative to the light bulb A, but relative to something else!!!

The **light bulb A** has emit photons towards all directions, but as we see on the **figure 7,(b)** , the photons that are emitted towards the East are closer to the **light bulb A** than the photons emitted towards the West, which means that we must say that the relative speed between the **light bulb A** and the photons moving towards the East is smaller than the relative speed between the **light bulb A** and the photons moving towards the West!!!!

Why what we see on the figure 7 is happening???

This is happening because the motion of the photons in the vicinity of the Earth is affected & determined by the gravity of the Earth!!!

The motion of the photons that are emitted by the **light bulbs A & B** will be the same(figures 6, 7), but their motion is also affected by the gravity of the Earth, and that's why the light waves created by the two light bulbs are expanding in the same way.

So, the photons that the two light bulbs/sources emit are making the same motion inside the gravitational field of the Earth!!!

The **light bulb A** is on the move inside the gravitational field due to the rotation of the Earth, and it will not be at the hypothetical centre of its own light wave!!!

The **light bulb B** is stationary inside the gravitational field of the Earth because it does not revolve around the Earth's axis, and it will be at the hypothetical centre of the light wave!!!

What I present in the **figures 5, 6 & 7** correlates to Quantum Physics, the Sagnac effect on the GPS systems, and the Michelson-Gale-Pearson experiment.

Regarding gravitational blueshift & redshift.

Suppose that we have a source of light located at some height above the surface of the Earth. It can be 10 metres, or 100 metres, or 1000 metres above the surface, it doesn't really matter as long as it's not too far from the planet.

The light source is placed exactly between two detectors that can detect the photons that the source will emit(**figures 8, 9**).

The one detector is at lower altitude and the other detector is at higher altitude and the source is exactly between them(**figures 8, 9**).

Light source and detectors are stationary relative to each other and are also stationary relative to the Earth.

At some point the light source emits photons towards all directions, meaning that a light wave will be created(**figure 8**).

(On the **figure 8** we see a two-dimensional wave. The light source actually emits a three-dimensional wave, but we cannot depict that.

In order to visualise how the light wave that we see in the **figure 8** will look like as a three-dimensional wave, you have to combine the **figure 8** with the **figures 6-7**)

The light source will not be at the hypothetical centre of the expanding light wave, as we see in the **figure 8!!!**

This will happen because the gravity of the Earth affects the motion of the photons and pulls them towards the planet(**figure 8**).

It's like if the gravity of the Earth pulls the whole light wave towards the planet, and as a result, the light source will not be at the centre of the light wave(**figure 8**).

When the photons will reach the two detectors(**figures 8, 9**), the interaction of the photons with the particles on the detectors will not be the same on the two detectors, meaning that the photoelectric effect, the Compton scattering, etc., will not be the same on the two detectors!!!

On the **figure 9** we see only two of the photons that are moving towards the detectors, instead of seeing the whole light wave.

The light source emits a light wave towards all directions meaning that it emits many photons towards all directions, but on the **figure 9** we see only two of these photons, and we see that the photon moving towards the Earth is farther away from the source, and the photon that is moving away from the Earth is closer to the light source.

The two detectors will not detect the same energy on the photons even though the light source has emitted identical photons towards all directions(figures 8, 9)!!!

The detector 1 will detect photons with higher energy(blueshift), meaning photons with higher frequency & shorter wavelength, and the detector 2 will detect photons with lower energy(redshift), meaning photons with lower frequency & larger wavelength!!!

Why the detectors will not detect the same energy on the photons, even though the light source has emitted identical photons towards all directions???

Let's see why.

The photons that are emitted by the light source are pulled by the gravity of the planet, and that's why the light source is not at the hypothetical centre of the light wave(**figure 8**)!!!

The reason why the detector 1 will detect photons with higher energy is obvious from what the **figure 8** shows.

The photons that are moving towards the Earth and the detector 1 will move faster because they are pulled by the gravity of the planet and that's why are farther away from the light source(figures 8, 9), and the photons that are moving away from the Earth and

towards the detector 2 will move slower because their motion is restrained by the gravity of the planet and that's why are closer to the source.

Figure 8

Figure 8. The light source will not be at the centre of the light wave. The light source will emit identical photons towards all directions but the two detectors will not detect the same photons. The detector 1 will detect photons with higher energy(blueshift) and the detector 2 will detect photons with lower energy(redshift).

So, the photons are not having the same speed relative to the source and also relative to the detectors!!!

If we compare the energy of the collision between the detector 1 and the photons with the energy of the collision between the detector 2 and the photons, we will find that the collision between the photons and the detector 1 has higher energy(**figure 9**), meaning that **we will say that the photons are having higher energy, but it is not the energy of the photons that is higher, instead it's the energy of the collision between the detector and the photons that is higher!!!**

The detector 1 will detect photons with higher energy(higher frequency & shorter wavelength) because **the energy of the collision** between the detector 1 and the photons will be larger due to the higher relative speed between the photons and the detector 1(**figure 9**).

The detector 2 will detect photons with lower energy(lower frequency & larger wavelength) because **the energy of the collision** between the detector 2 and the photons will be lower due to the slower relative speed between the photons and the detector 2(**figure 9**).

Figure 9

Figure 9. The detector 1 will detect photons with higher energy, and the detector 2 will detect photons with lower energy.

As you see, my explanation regarding gravitational redshift and blueshift is different from what general relativity proposes, and derives from the fact that light sources are not located at the hypothetical centre of the light wave that they emit towards all directions.

The scientific community believes that light sources are at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that they emit towards all directions, but as I demonstrate on this paper, this is wrong.

If a light source is at the hypothetical centre of the light wave that it emits towards all directions, this means that the motion of light relative to this source is the same towards all directions (isotropic), but as I demonstrate on this paper, this is not what is happening!

The motion of light relative to its source is anisotropic because the reality is that light sources are not located at the hypothetical centre of the spherical light waves that they emit towards all directions, and this regards most light sources on the Universe!

This leads to the detection of different energy on the photons emitted from a source, dependent on direction.

My ideas correlate with the ideas of Quantum Physics!

Regarding changes in the energy of photons in general.

On the examples in the **figures 5, 6 & 7**, we have seen that a light source which is stationary on the surface of the Earth will not be at the hypothetical centre of the light waves that it will emit.

Now let's see something else about a source that is stationary on the surface of the Earth, that is related to what I have said on the examples in the **figures 8 & 9** about the redshift and the blueshift.

Suppose that we have a source of light placed on the Equator, and it is stationary relative to the surface of the Earth(**figure 10**).

The light source is placed exactly between two detectors that can detect the photons that the source will emit(**figure 10**).

The two detectors are also placed on the Equator, and the one detector(detector 1) is placed towards the direction of the West relative to the light source, and the other detector(detector 2) is placed towards the direction of the East relative to the source(**figure 10**).

Light source and detectors are stationary relative to each other.

Source and detectors are moving towards the East due to the rotation of the Earth(**figure 10**).

At some point the light source emits photons towards all directions, meaning that a light wave will be created(**figure 10**).

The light source will not be at the hypothetical centre of the light wave due to the rotation of the Earth, as we see in the **figure 10**, and as I have explain in the **figures 5, 6 & 7** at the beginning of this paper.

(The light source that we see in the **figure 10** it's in the same situation with the light bulb A in the **figures 5, 6 & 7**).

When the photons will reach the two detectors(**figure 10**), the interaction of the photons with the particles on the detectors will not be the same on the two detectors, meaning that the photoelectric effect, the Compton scattering, etc., will not be the same on the two detectors!!!

On the previous example I have used two pictures(figures 8 & 9), and in the **figure 8** we see a light wave and in the **figure 9** we see only two of the photons that consist the light wave, but on this example I use only one picture(the **figure 10**), and on the **figure 10** we see both the light wave and two of the photons that consist the light wave, and these two photons will collide with the detectors.

The two detectors will not detect the same energy on the photons even though the source has emit identical photons towards all directions(figure 10)!!!

The detector 1 will detect photons with higher energy(blueshift), meaning photons with higher frequency & shorter wavelength, and the detector 2 will detect photons with lower energy(redshift), meaning photons with lower frequency & larger wavelength!!!

Why the detectors will not detect the same energy on the photons, even though the light source has emit identical photons towards all directions???

Let's see why.

Due to the rotation of the Earth the light source and the detectors are moving towards the East, meaning that the source will not be at the hypothetical centre of its own light wave(**figure 10**)!

The detector 1 will collide with the photons that the source has emit towards the West, and the detector 2 will collide with the photons that the source has emit towards the East.

If we compare the **energy of the collision** between the detector 1 and the photons with the **energy of the collision** between the detector 2 and the photons, we will find that the collision between the photons and the detector 1 has higher energy(**figure 10**), meaning that we will say that the photons are having higher energy!!!

Due to the rotation of the Earth the detector 1 is moving towards the East, but the photons with which will collide are moving towards the West!!

So, the photons that are emitted towards the West are moving towards the detector 1, and the detector 1 is moving towards the photons because it is moving towards the East due to the rotation of the Earth(**figure 10**), and due to that, the **energy of the collision** between the photons and the detector 1 will be **higher!!!**

The photons that are emitted towards the East are moving towards the detector 2, and the detector 2 is also moving towards the East due to the rotation of the Earth(**figure 10**), and it's like if the detector 2 is trying to move away from the photons, and due to that, **the energy of the collision** between the photons and the detector 2 will be **lower!!!**

What I demonstrate on the figure 10, and also on the figure 5, 6 & 7, correlates with the "Sagnac effect" on the GPS systems, the Michelson-Gale-Pearson experiment and the ideas of Quantum Physics!

Figure 10

Figure 10. The light source and the detectors are moving towards the East due to the rotation of the Earth. The source will emit identical photons towards all directions but the two detectors will not detect the same photons. The detector 1 will detect photons with higher energy(blueshift) and the detector 2 will detect photons with lower energy(redshift).

As we see in the **figure 10**, the detector 1 is closer to the expanding light wave than the detector 2 because the detector 1 is moving towards the light wave and the detector 2 is moving away from the light wave, and this is happening because the detectors are moving towards the East due to the rotation of the Earth!!!

The detector 1 will detect photons with higher energy (higher frequency & shorter wavelength) due to the higher relative speed between the photons and the detector 1, and the detector 2 will detect photons with lower energy (lower frequency & larger wavelength) due to the lower relative speed between the photons and the detector 2 (**figure 10**).

Conclusion.

General and Special Relativity are wrong!

They do not describe the reality regarding the motion of light.

Most of the light sources on the Universe are not located at the hypothetical centre of the wave of light that they emit towards all directions!

It cannot be otherwise!

If we have a million light sources in relative motion with each other at the same location, only one source may be at the hypothetical centre of the wave of light that they emit towards all directions.

This means that the motion of light is anisotropic relative to its source, and as a result we have the detection of different energy on the photons emitted by the source, dependent on direction, even though the source emits identical photons towards all directions!

The ideas on this paper correlate with Quantum Physics, the Michelson-Gale-Pearson experiment, and the "Sagnac effect" on the GPS systems (and the Sagnac effect in general).